

THE ESSENCE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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The development of communicative competence in teaching English is a multifaceted and dynamic process that goes beyond mere language proficiency. It encompasses the ability to effectively and appropriately use the English language in various real-life communication contexts, taking into account sociocultural norms, pragmatic aspects, and the interplay of linguistic skills. Here's a breakdown of the essence of developing communicative competence in teaching English:

Holistic Language Proficiency

Communicative competence focuses on equipping learners with a holistic set of language skills, including not only grammatical and lexical knowledge but also functional and pragmatic competencies. This includes the ability to understand and convey meaning in various communication situations, such as social interactions, workplace communication, and academic settings.

Linguistic Skills and Strategies

Teaching communicative competence involves nurturing learners' receptive and productive language skills, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Moreover, it emphasizes the development of language learning strategies that empower students to comprehend and express themselves effectively in English across different contexts.

Sociocultural and Pragmatic Awareness

An integral aspect of communicative competence is the cultivation of sociocultural and pragmatic awareness. This entails understanding the cultural norms, etiquette, and communicative conventions that shape language use. Students learn to adapt their language and behavior to appropriately navigate diverse cultural and social settings where English is spoken.

Interaction and Collaboration

The development of communicative competence encourages interactive and collaborative learning experiences. Students engage in communicative tasks, role-plays, discussions, and real-world simulations that encourage active participation, negotiation of meaning, and the application of language in authentic communicative contexts.

Authentic Materials and Contexts

Effective teaching of communicative competence integrates authentic materials and contexts, exposing learners to real-life language use through genuine texts, multimedia resources, and contextualized exercises. This approach immerses students in the practical application of language skills, fostering a deeper understanding of language in use.

Learner-Centered Approach

A learner-centered approach is fundamental to developing communicative competence. It involves tailoring instruction to meet the individual needs, interests, and goals of learners, thereby promoting a more personalized and effective language learning experience.

Assessment of Functional Language Proficiency

Assessing communicative competence involves evaluating students' functional language proficiency, their ability to use English in meaningful and authentic ways. Assessment methods may include performance-based tasks, oral presentations, group discussions, and written communication tasks that gauge students' communicative abilities.

Language for Global Citizenship

In the context of a globalized world, communicative competence in English extends beyond linguistic skills; it fosters intercultural understanding, global citizenship, and cross-cultural communication. This emphasizes the importance of promoting empathy, open-mindedness, and respectful engagement across diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

By emphasizing the development of communicative competence in English language teaching, educators aim to equip learners with the linguistic, sociocultural, and pragmatic skills necessary to navigate and succeed in multilingual and multicultural environments.

Currently, "autonomy" is heavily used as an important term as a student-oriented approach to teaching English is becoming more popular instead of a teacher-oriented method. The term autonomous language acquisition has been defined by several scholars. As described by Henry Holec, who developed autonomous education, "the ability to undertake one's own education is the responsibility to make decisions on all aspects of Education". However, T. Trebbi argues that without a student being responsible for the educational process himself, there will be no learning and development - "taking charge of one's own education" is a naturally occurring act. P. Benson and P. Foller believes that autonomous education is a self-regulatory responsibility in the process of reading and is a sign of a higher academic performance. D. Littl, on the other

hand, defines autonomous education as the ability to independently complete assignments with deep understanding. R.L.Oxford defines autonomous education more broadly in relation to other scholars as follows, "a movement that reflects the ability and desire to consciously and purposefully perform a task without any assistance, using appropriate educational strategies, adapted to the requirements of a different situation . L.As defined by the Dem, autonomous education is the ability, or desire, to enter into a social attitude to learn alone or in collaboration with others in a sense of responsibility. In some sources, autonomous education is confused with independent education, but these two terms are not synonymous. Independent education is education without a teacher, without peers, independent study, but some computer program can be used as an assistant. According to B. Kumaravadivelu, in the autonomous study of English, students work in collaboration with their teachers and peers, the university administration. After the analysis of research work, autonomous education can be summarized as follows: autonomous education is the ability to learn an independent foreign language with a little help from a teacher and enter into a social relationship with peers to work in cooperation.

Considered a requirement of time, autonomous education plays an important role in teaching English. If students are seeking to complete assignments autonomously, they must be supported, resulting in academic success for students. D.As Baume notes, autonomous education should be one of the most important goals of the higher education system so that students studying foreign languages are involved in autonomous education and take responsibility for their academic achievements. When students learn English autonomously, they are expected to associate the knowledge gained with the real world, resulting in learning in this way becoming a vital acquisition rather than memorization.

While autonomous learning dominates teaching a foreign language with many advantages, some of its disadvantages prevent effective language teaching. P.Van argues that when practicing autonomous education and teaching a foreign language, the following negative situations may arise: (a) forcing students to make independent decisions; (B) wasting time; (D) renouncing teaching habits; (e) criticizing students . Usually in traditional education, since in the classroom the teacher makes a decision, it is quite natural that at the beginning it seems difficult for students to find out what to learn and how to learn independently. The reason why students make wrong decisions is to achieve the intended goal is to spend a long time mastering a foreign language. Of course, in such

conditions, the teacher must solve the problem by correcting the mistakes of students, providing guidance and advice. Teachers spend a lot of time creating new ones due to the inability to find suitable exercises for autonomous education in the textbook. At first, it is natural that it will take a long time to adapt or create a new assignment, but later the problem of spending a lot of time is solved as the teacher can assemble the adapted/created materials as an exercise portfolio and process it by making some adjustments for other groups.

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